

SZ-BB-II-02-02 Creating a presentation together (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14851216
ID	SZ-BB-II-02-02
Title	Creating a presentation together
Educational area	#vocational-training
Persona	P: Jasper - Trainee https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091281
Short description	Jasper is an industrial mechanic apprentice at Zeiss and has to prepare a presentation for his economics class together with his classmates.
Result	Jasper and his classmates find a shared digital space in BIRD where they can collaborate more efficiently and exchange ideas directly when they have questions.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario• Process: "creating a project in BIRD"
Preconditions	BIRD registration and BIRD access data
Components	#chat #workspace #contacts
Services / tools	Haiku Check, text editing, Platform used by the vocational school

Problem scenario

Introduction

Jasper Kempe is a first-year apprentice. He and some of his classmates are supposed to give a presentation for their vocational school. They are to research a topic in the field of economics and give a presentation on it. Since the others are in different companies and therefore don't see each other very often during the week, they decide to collaborate digitally.

Problem definition

Based on the decision to collaborate digitally, Jasper is wondering how they could all simultaneously edit and comment on a shared document (for example slide deck, poster, mini-movie/screencast, board, etc.) that they want to use during the

presentation. He needs a suitable solution for this.

At the same time, it would be beneficial if this solution also supported group work through a shared calendar, appointment reminders, and opportunities for collaborative online exchange. Since Jasper is not a native speaker, inclusive elements such as spell check and terminology explanations are important to him. It's also important to Jasper and his classmates that the system handles their data in a trustworthy manner.

Background and context

Jasper knows he's not the best at time management. Finishing his assignments on time is a challenge for him. And it's even more important in group work, as shared agreements must be adhered to. As a non-native speaker, Jasper isn't always sure he has understood the assignments' conversations when they quickly explain something to him. Even though they're considerate most of the time and ask if he understood everything, this still presents an additional challenge.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Jasper wants to be involved, just like everyone else. The young people are having trouble coordinating tasks — whether at meetings at the vocational school or virtually. They definitely need to find a better way to collaborate. The presentation has to be finished by a certain time. Jasper and his classmates not only want to understand the topic they're working on, but also want to get a good grade for their presentation.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Jasper's group has met once so far after class. One classmate had the presentation template on his computer, the others looked at it, and "discussed it" a bit. However, this way, not everyone has direct access to the document — the individual pieces would have to be combined in an additional step. Working in a shared digital space would be much more efficient, and they could discuss questions directly, instead of having to wait for the next meeting or exchange messages via other means.

Activity scenario

Process "creating a project in BIRD"

Step 1: Jasper creates the project "The magic square of the economics balance sheet" in his workspace. The group had already discussed this at school before everyone had to leave. Jasper had agreed to do it.

Step 2: He then drags a text editor into the project and shares it with the other trainees. Sharing is done via the contact search and the respective name. Using a chat function

in the contact area, he informs his classmates that the shared document has been successfully created and asks what they should do next.

Step 3: His classmates get in touch after a short while, and together they decide what needs to be done and who will take on which tasks. They even decide on a specific presentation tool.

Step 4: Jasper incorporates the tool "[Haiku Deck: Presentation Software and Online Presentation Tools](#)" into the joint project. The shared project area now give him access to Haiku Deck, where he logs in using single sign on.

Step 5: After Jasper has browsed suitable slide designs and the others have shared some favorites in the chat, they select a suitable one by voting. Now the collaborative development can begin. Jasper can track in real time how a trainee inserts sales statistics in the form of graphics. Another writes the explanatory text and adds additional diagrams. Yet another takes on the part about cost-benefit analyses and adds tables. Jasper enjoys taking care of the design and always adapts it on the spot.

Step 6: Unlike his classmates, Jasper is still very unsure about German grammar and has trouble finding the "right" words. Therefore, he uses a technical writing aid based on artificial intelligence to formulate his speaking parts. He then asks the others what they think and whether they can correct any mistakes. Unfortunately, he couldn't find this tool in the shared workspace and had to use it externally.

Step 7: One trainee raises a few questions and comments on data he doesn't fully understand. Jasper responds directly to his comments, clarifies any ambiguities, and provides additional information. The team uses BIRD's integrated chat to discuss progress and upcoming tasks.

Step 8: Jasper now receives a reminder from his calendar that he has a meeting that day. The group communicates mostly through comments in shared documents and chat, but they've agreed to meet again a few days before the presentation.

Step 9: Jasper logs into the platform used by the vocational school using single sign on. He starts a video conference within the platform so the group can review the entire presentation and make final adjustments.

Step 10: After completing the work, they send the presentation link to their teacher to receive advance feedback.

Step 11: Based on the teacher's comments and suggestions, they make final adjustments.